

MUHANDISLIK

& IQTISODIYOT

No1

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

2026 yanvar

Milliy nashrlar

OAK: <https://oak.uz/pages/4802>

05.00.00 - Texnika fanlari

08.00.00 - Iqtisodiyot fanlar

Google Scholar

OPEN ACCESS

ULRICHSWEB[™]
GLOBAL SERIALS DIRECTORY

Academic Resource Index
ResearchBib

ISSN INTERNATIONAL STANDARD SERIAL NUMBER INTERNATIONAL CENTRE

CYBERLENINKA

OpenAIRE

ROAD

INDEX COPERNICUS INTERNATIONAL

BASE

Crossref

НАУЧНАЯ ЭЛЕКТРОННАЯ БИБЛИОТЕКА LIBRARY.RU

ISSN: 3060-463X

РЭУ.РФ
РОССИЙСКИЙ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИЙ УНИВЕРСИТЕТ
ИМЕНИ Г.В. ПЛЕХАНОВА
ТАШКЕНТСКИЙ ФИЛИАЛ

muhandislik **& iqtisodiyot**

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

Elektron nashr, 534 sahifa.
2026-yil, yanvar

Bosh muharrir:

Zokirova Nodira Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, DSc, professor

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Shakarov Zafar G'afurovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori, PhD, dotsent

Tahrir hay'ati:

Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayevich, O'z FA akademigi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Sharipov Kongratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori, professor

Maxkamov Baxtiyor Shuxratovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Shaumarov Said Sanatovich, texnika fanlari doktori, professor

Turayev Bahodir Xatamovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Nasimov Dilmurod Abdulloyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Allayeva Gulchexra Jalgasovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Arabov Nurali Uralovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Maxmudov Odiljon Xolmirzayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Xamrayeva Sayyora Nasimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Bobonazarova Jamila Xolmurodovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Irmatova Aziza Baxromovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Bo'taboyev Mahammadjon To'ychiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Shamshiyeva Nargizaxon Nosirxuja kizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor,

Xolmuxamedov Muhsinjon Murodullayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Xodjayeva Nodiraxon Abdurashidovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Amanov Otabek Amankulovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent

Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Qurbonov Samandar Pulatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Zikriyoyev Aziz Sadulloyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Tabayev Azamat Zaripbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Sxay Lana Aleksandrovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent

Ismoilova Gulnora Fayzullayevna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Djumaniyazov Umrbek Iloxamovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Kasimova Nargiza Sabitdjanovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Kalanova Moxigul Baxritdinovna, dotsent

Ashurzoda Luiza Muxtarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Sharipov Sardor Begmaxmat o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Sharipov Botirali Roxataliyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor

Tursunov Ulug'bek Sativoldiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent

Bauyetdinov Majit Janizaqovich, Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti dotsenti, PhD

Botirov Bozorbek Musurmon o'g'li, Texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Sultonov Shavkatjon Abdullayevich, Kimyo fanlari doktori, (DSc)

Jo'raeva Malohat Muhammadovna, filologiya fanlari doktori (DSc), professor.

Yusupov Maxamadamin Abduxamidovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi (DSc), professor

Kalonova Moxigul Baxritdinovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi (PhD), dotsent

Mirzayev Kulmamat Djanzakovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi (DSc), professor.

Karimova Nilufar Sadirdin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Norboyev Odil Abrayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent

Nasimov Dilmurod Abdulloyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

muhandislik & iqtisodiyot

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

- 05.01.00 – Axborot texnologiyalari, boshqaruv va kompyuter grafikasi
- 05.01.01 – Muhandislik geometriyasi va kompyuter grafikasi. Audio va video texnologiyalari
- 05.01.02 – Tizimli tahlil, boshqaruv va axborotni qayta ishlash
- 05.01.03 – Informatikaning nazariy asoslari
- 05.01.04 – Hisoblash mashinalari, majmualari va kompyuter tarmoqlarining matematik va dasturiy ta'minoti
- 05.01.05 – Axborotlarni himoyalash usullari va tizimlari. Axborot xavfsizligi
- 05.01.06 – Hisoblash texnikasi va boshqaruv tizimlarining elementlari va qurilmalari
- 05.01.07 – Matematik modellashtirish
- 05.01.11 – Raqamli texnologiyalar va sun'iy intellekt
- 05.02.00 – Mashinasozlik va mashinashunoslik
- 05.02.08 – Yer usti majmualari va uchish apparatlari
- 05.03.02 – Metrologiya va metrologiya ta'minoti
- 05.04.01 – Telekommunikatsiya va kompyuter tizimlari, telekommunikatsiya tarmoqlari va qurilmalari. Axborotlarni taqsimlash
- 05.05.03 – Yorug'lik texnikasi. Maxsus yoritish texnologiyasi
- 05.05.05 – Issiqlik texnikasining nazariy asoslari
- 05.05.06 – Qayta tiklanadigan energiya turlari asosidagi energiya qurilmalari
- 05.06.01 – To'qimachilik va yengil sanoat ishlab chiqarishlari materialshunosligi
- 05.08.03 – Temir yo'l transportini ishlatish
- 05.09.01 – Qurilish konstruksiyalari, bino va inshootlar
- 05.09.04 – Suv ta'minoti. Kanalizatsiya. Suv havzalarini muhofazalovchi qurilish tizimlari
- 10.00.06 – Qiyosiy adabiyotshunoslik, chog'ishtirma tilshunoslik va tarjimashunoslik
- 10.00.04 – Yevropa, Amerika va Avstraliya xalqlari tili va adabiyoti
- 08.00.01 – Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 – Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 – Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 – Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 – Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 – Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 – Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 – Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 – Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 – Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 – Marketing
- 08.00.12 – Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 – Menejment
- 08.00.14 – Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 – Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 – Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 – Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Ma'lumot uchun, OAK
Rayosatining 2024-yil 28-avgustdagi 360/5-son qarori bilan "Dissertatsiyalar asosiy ilmiy natijalarini chop etishga tavsiya etilgan milliy ilmiy nashrlar ro'yxati"ga texnika va iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha "Muhandislik va iqtisodiyot" jurnali ro'yxatga kiritilgan.

Muassis: "Tadbirkor va ishbilarmon" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz:

1. Toshkent shahridagi G.V.Plexanov nomidagi Rossiya iqtisodiyot universiteti
2. Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti
3. Toshkent irrigatsiya va qishloq xo'jaligini mexanizatsiyalash muhandislari instituti" milliy tadqiqot universiteti
4. Islom Karimov nomidagi Toshkent davlat texnika universiteti
5. Muhammad al-Xorazmiy nomidagi Toshkent axborot texnologiyalari universiteti
6. Toshkent davlat transport universiteti
7. Toshkent arxitektura-qurilish universiteti
8. Toshkent kimyo-texnologiya universiteti
9. Jizzax politexnika instituti

MUNDARIJA

ИНСТИТУЦИОНАЛЬНЫЕ И ТЕХНОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ ЦИФРОВОЙ ТРАНСФОРМАЦИИ ЖЕЛЕЗНОДОРОЖНОГО ТРАНСПОРТА УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	26
Каракулов Фарход Зайпудинович	
TRANSPORT TIZIMIGA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARNI JORIY ETISH VA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH USULLARI	33
Bababekova Gulchexra Baxtiyarovna	
QURILISH MATERIALLARI ISHLAB CHIQUARUVCHI KORXONALARNING SIFAT MENEJMENTI TIZIMINI BAHOLASH	38
Achilov Ilmurad Nematovich	
TURIZM OBYEKTLARINI RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA RIVOJLANTIRISHNING TASHKILY-IQTISODIY MEKANIZMLARI.....	45
Toshtemirov Xojiakbar Qahramon o'g'li	
КАЧЕСТВО КРЕДИТНОГО ПОРТФЕЛЯ БАНКОВ УЗБЕКИСТАНА ЧЕРЕЗ ПРИЗМУ ПРОБЛЕМНЫХ КРЕДИТОВ	51
Алиева Сусанна Сейрановна	
ВЛИЯНИЕ ЛИБЕРАЛИЗАЦИИ И РЫНОЧНЫХ МЕХАНИЗМОВ НА РАЗВИТИЕ ОБЩЕВОДСТВА И КАРАКУЛЕВОДСТВА В ГЛОБАЛЬНОМ МАСШТАБЕ	58
Нуриллаев Жамолиддин Ярашевич	
BARQAROR INVESTITSIYALAR: IQTISODIYOTDAGI ROLI VA DOLZARBLIGI	65
Ruzibayeva Nargiza Xakimovna	
KRAUDFANDING – BARQAROR RIVOJLANISHNI AMALGA OSHIRISH UCHUN INNOVATSION MOLIYAVIY VOSITA SIFATIDA.....	71
Ashurova Oltin Yuldashevna	
FUQAROLIK JAMIYATI INSTITUTLARINI DAVLAT TOMONIDAN QO'LLAB-QUVVATLASHDA MOLIYAVIY BOSHQARUV SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH MASALALARI.....	78
Xusanova Gulsum Baxtiyorovna	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI MAHSULOTLARI UCHUN BARQAROR BREND QIYMATINI SHAKLLANTIRISH STRATEGIYALARI	84
Bekmurod Davlatmurotovich Ollaberganov, Zilola Baxramovna Abdikarimova	
TADBIRKORLIK SUBYEKTLARI INVESTITSION JOZIBADORLIGINI OSHIRISHDA KORPORATIV BOSHQARUVNING O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI	89
Atajanov Kamal Atavayevich	
AVTOTRANSFORMATORLARNING TASHQI MAGNIT MAYDONINING MATEMATIK MODELI	96
Pirmatov Nurali Berdiyrovich, Bekishev Allabergen Yergashevich, Baxriddinov Begzod Alibek o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTON VA JAHON AMALIYOTIDA BUDJET MUASSASALARIDA BUXGALTERIYA HISOBINING RIVOJLANISHIGA RETROSPEKTIV TAHLIL	101
Berdiyev Toshkenboy Panjiyevich	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA MUAMMOLI KREDITLARNI BOSHQARISH TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH: RISKGA ASOSLANGAN YONDASHUV VA AMALIY MEKANIZMLAR	108
Tojiyev Sardor Dilmurod o'g'li	
TIJORAT BANKLARI DEPOZIT BAZASINI MUSTAHKAMLASHNING O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI	113
Shayxiyev Boburbek Ulug'bekovich	
DAVLAT-XUSUSIY SHERIKLIGI ASOSIDA OLIY TA'LIM TIZIMINI TRANSFORMATSIYA QILISHNING KONSEPTUAL MODELI.....	120
Abdullayev Javohir Abdumalik o'g'li	

GEODEZIYA VA GIS TEXNOLOGIYALARINING INTEGRATSIYASI.....	125
<i>Ziynura sabirova</i>	
RESPUBLIKADA UY-JOY QURILISHI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHDA DAVLAT VA XUSUSIY SEKTOR HAMKORLIGINING O'RNI	129
<i>Otajonov Tohirjon Xo'janazar o'g'li</i>	
СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ СИСТЕМЫ СОЦИАЛЬНО-ТРУДОВЫХ ОТНОШЕНИЙ НА ПРЕДПРИЯТИЯХ ЖЕЛЕЗНОДОРОЖНОГО ТРАНСПОРТА АО «УЗБЕКИСТОН ТЕМИР ЙУЛЛАРИ» В УСЛОВИЯХ СТРУКТУРНЫХ РЕФОРМ.....	133
<i>Кадирова Шарофат Амоновна</i>	
KASBLARNI MODERNIZATSIYA QILISH VA MEHNAT BOZORINING YANGI MODELINI BARPO ETISH	139
<i>Ruziyev Oybek Abdumuminovich, Nurboyev Jaloliddin Mamadiyevich</i>	
O'ZBEKISTONDA AVTOMOBIL BIZNESINING RIVOJLANISH TENDENSIYALARI	143
<i>Saidov Dilshodbek Razzakovich</i>	
QISHLOQ JOYLARIDA MEHNAT RESURSLARIDAN FOYDALANISH SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASH USULLARI	148
<i>Amaniyazova Rayhan Bayniyazovna</i>	
ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКАЯ ОЦЕНКА ЭКСПЛУАТАЦИОННОЙ УСТОЙЧИВОСТИ МАЛОМОЩНЫХ СЕТЕВЫХ СОЛНЕЧНЫХ ФОТОЭЛЕКТРИЧЕСКИХ СТАНЦИЙ В УСЛОВИЯХ УЗБЕКИСТАНА	153
<i>Кудратов Афзалхужа Рустамович, Далмурадова Наргиза Нуриллаевна, Шогучкаров Санжар Кодирович</i>	
MINTAQADA PARRANDACHILIK SANOATINI RIVOJLANTIRISHGA TA'SIR ETUVCHI OMILLAR VA ULARNING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIKKA TA'SIRI	161
<i>Qarshiyev Obidjon Egamberdiyevich</i>	
INNOVATSION BANK EKOTIZIMLARINING TIJORAT BANKLARI RIVOJLANISHIDAGI ROLI	165
<i>Aliyev Hasan Rayimjonovich</i>	
ANALYSIS OF FACTORS OF INTENSIVE ECONOMIC GROWTH IN UZBEKISTAN	171
<i>Sharipov Kamil</i>	
SUN'IY INTELLEKT – TO'RTINCHI SANOAT INQILOBINING ASOSI.....	176
<i>Kalonov Muxiddin Baxriddinovich</i>	
KORXONALARDA MOLIVAVIY BOSHQARUVNING TASHKILY VA IQTISODIY MASALALARI.....	187
<i>Jumayev Samariddin Ziyodullaevich</i>	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT KONSEPSIYASI ASOSIDA KICHIK BIZNES FAOLIYATINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI	193
<i>Isroilov Dilshodbek Rustamovich</i>	
TALABALARDA O'Z-O'ZINI TARTIBGA SOLISH KO'NIKMALARINING RIVOJLANISHIDA INTERAKTIV TA'LIM PLATFORMALARINING O'RNI	198
<i>Bozorova Muazzam Hamid qizi, Hakimova Gulnora Abdullo qizi, Hakimova Mushtariybonu Hamid qizi</i>	
XIZMAT KO'RSATISH TARMOQLARIDA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA SHAROITIDA MONOPOLIYAGA QARSHI NAZORATNING XORIJIY TAJRIBASI	203
<i>Bekbutayev Nodirjon Fayzullayevich</i>	
XORAZM VILOYATIDA KAMBAG'ALLIK DARAJASINING O'ZGARISHI VA BU JARAYONGA TA'SIR ETUVCHI OMILLAR TAHLILI.....	208
<i>Mayliyeva Sadoqat Safayozovna</i>	
IQTISODIY-MATEMATIK VA SSENARIYLI YONDASHUVLARDAN FOYDALANIB SANOAT RIVOJLANISHINI BAHOLASH VA PROGNOZLASH	213
<i>Turdiyev Ulug'bek Qayumovich, Qayumova Nurafshona Ulug'bek qizi</i>	
EKSPORTNI RIVOJLANTIRISH STRATEGIYALARINING DOLZARBLIGI.....	217
<i>Abdivaliyev Shahzodbek Xayrullayevich, Mutalov Sultonbek Abduraim o'g'li, Baymanova Mavlyuda Djurayevna, Ubaydullayeva Gulchexra Erkabayevna, Aipova Iroda Ikramovna</i>	

LEGAL AND INSTITUTIONAL FOUNDATIONS OF ECONOMIC COOPERATION BETWEEN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN AND INTERNATIONAL FINANCIAL INSTITUTIONS	222
Yovkochev Sherzod	
ICHKI AUDIT FUNKSIYALARINING ICHKI NAZORATNI TA'MINLASHDAGI AHAMIYATI	228
Tursunov Shohruxmirzo Baxtiyor o'g'li	
MOSH DONINI YANCHIB OLISHDA QO'LLANILADIGAN QURILMANI LOYIHALASH	232
Qurbanov Abdimalik Jo'rayevich	
DAVLAT BOSHQARUVIDA SAMARADORLIKNI BAHOLASH: INSTITUTSIONAL MEXANIZMLAR, RAQAMLI YECHIMLAR VA AMALIY KUTILMALAR	239
Sarvar Saidov Xayrulloevich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA TURIZMNI RIVOJLANTIRISH KONSEPSIYASI DOIRASIDA UNING INFRATUZILMASINI TASHKILIY-IQTISODIY MEXANIZMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH BORASIDA TAVSIYALAR	244
Tashov Mizrob Maxmudovich	
DAVLAT BOSHQARUV ORGANLARIDA INSON KAPITALINI BOSHQARISHNING TASHKILIY-IQTISODIY MEXANIZMLARI	251
Mashrabaliyev Ibroximbek Mashrabaliyevich	
ФИНАНСЫ И ВЫСШАЯ МАТЕМАТИКА В КОНТЕКСТЕ ГЛОБАЛЬНОГО РАЗВИТИЯ ЦИФРОВОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ И ПРЕДПРИНИМАТЕЛЬСТВА	257
Айматова Фариди Хуразовна	
ZAMONAVIY IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARNING ROLI	263
Salayeva Dilafro'z Aybekovna	
ДИАГНОСТИКА СИНХРОННОГО ДВИГАТЕЛЯ НА ОСНОВЕ ИЗМЕРЕНИЯ ВНЕШНЕГО МАГНИТНОГО ПОЛЯ	267
Пирматов Нурали Бердярович, Бекишев Аллаберген Ергашевич, Мамуров Алмас Жумабой угли	
XORIJIIY MAMLAKATLAR TAJRIBASI ASOSIDA SANOAT KORXONALARIDA INNOVATSION FAOLIYATNI RIVOJLANTIRISH YO'NALISHLARI VA XUSUSIYATLARI	275
Kurbanova Shaxnoza Yuldashbayevna	
СТРАТЕГИЧЕСКАЯ ОЦЕНКА СТОИМОСТИ КОМПАНИИ В СДЕЛКАХ СЛИЯНИЙ И ПОГЛОЩЕНИЙ	279
Ли Илларион Георгиевич	
KO'P YADROLI CPU VA GPU ARXITEKTURALARIDA DIFFERENSIAL TENGLAMALARNI SONLI YECHISH UCHUN PARALLEL ALGORITMLARNI ISHLAB CHIQUISH VA SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASH	284
Ismailov Shixnazar Rashid o'g'li, Ubaydullayev Farrux Fathulla o'g'li, Odilov Asliddin Isoq o'g'li	
СИСТЕМАТИЧЕСКОЕ СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ НАЛОГООБЛОЖЕНИЯ — ОСНОВА ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ЭКОНОМИКИ	291
Муталов Абдуазим	
O'ZBEKISTONDA INVESTITSIYALARNING HUDUDIIY TARKIBI VA UNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'NALISHLARI	295
Ermamatov Shonazar Jumakulovich	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA INVESTITSIYA SIYOSATI: INSTITUTSIONAL VA RAQAMLI ISLOHOTLAR	302
Sobirov Yo'ldoshboy Ro'zimboevich	
QASHQADARYO VILOYATINING IJTIMOIIY-IQTISODIY SALOHIIYATI VA BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI	310
Tuyev Abdurahmon Yusubopvich	
TEMIR YO'L STANSIYALARIDA STRELKALI O'TKAZGICH QURILMALARI BO'YICHA YO'L QO'YILGAN NOSOZLIKLAR VA ULARNING TAHLILI	315
Yunusova Gulshanoy Umarali qizi	

SANOAT KORXONALARIDA ASOSIY FONDLARDAN VA ISHLAB CHIQRISH QUVVATIDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH YO'LLARI.....	320
Ulashev Xubbim Askarovich	
TURLI YO'L SHAROITLARIDA TO'QNASHUV PAYTIDA TORMOZLASH VA BOSHQARUV PARAMETRLARI	324
Uralbayev Anvar Ubaydullayevich	
YANGI YARATILGAN MAHALLIY DURAGAY PILLALARNI YAKKA CHUVISH NATIJALARINING TAHLILI.....	328
Sobirov Qo'ziboy Erkinovich	
UY-JOY KOMMUNAL XIZMAT KO'RSATISHNI ZAMONAVIY YO'LLARI.....	332
Boboqulov S.B.	
TARJIMON DASTURLARIDA MULTITILLARNI TASNIFLASH: MAVJUD YONDOSHUVLAR VA MUAMMOLAR	338
Maxmudjanova Sayyora Yashin qizi	
KICHIK BIZNES SUBYEKTLARIDA ICHKI AXBOROT TIZIMLARINING MODERNIZATSIYASI ORQALI ISHLAB CHIQRISH JARAYONLARINI OPTIMALLASHTIRISH	343
Yo'ldoshev Nodirbek Ne'matjon o'g'li	
NEFT VA GAZ TERMINOLOGIYASINING SHAKLLANISHI VA RIVOJLANISHINING NAZARIY ASOSLARI.....	349
Jo'rayeva Malohat Muhammadovna, Quryozova Gulshan Akmal qizi	
УСИЛЕНИЕ РОЛИ МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫХ ДЕНЕЖНЫХ ПЕРЕВОДОВ В ДОСТИЖЕНИИ УСТОЙЧИВОГО ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РОСТА В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	355
Гимранова О. Б.	
TIJORAT BANKLARI FAOLIYATINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA INVESTITSIYA OPERATSIYALARINING AHAMIYATI.....	361
Yuldashev Fozil Turapovich	
QO'SHILGAN QIYMAT SOLIG'INI HISOBLASH VA UNDIRISH MEKANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING DOLZARB MASALALARI	373
Jumanazarov Alisher Toshtemir o'g'li	
ВЛИЯНИЕ КАЧЕСТВА ПУБЛИЧНОГО ФИНАНСОВОГО УПРАВЛЕНИЯ НА ДИНАМИКУ ЭКОНОМИКИ	377
Наимов Шохрух Шарофиддинович	
DIVIDEND SIYOSATINI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA FOYDA SIFATI VA FOYDANI BOSHQARISHNING TA'SIRI.....	383
Eshev Furqat A'zamovich	
ТРАНСФОРМАЦИЯ СИСТЕМЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ УМНЫМ ГОРОДОМ НА БАЗЕ ЦИФРОВЫХ ПЛАТФОРМ С ОРИЕНТАЦИЕЙ НА ЧЕЛОВЕКА	388
Рахимова Мадина Шухрат кизи	
XO'JALIK YURITUVCHI SUBYEKTLARDA HISOB SIYOSATINING USLUBIY JIHATLARI	393
Toshpo'latov A. A.	
MOLIYAVIY HISOBOT ISHONCHLILIGINI OSHIRISH YO'NALISHLARI.....	398
Zufarova Zilola Rahim qizi	
RAQAMLI PUL TIZIMINING KORRUPSIYA VA YASHIRIN IQTISODIYOTGA QARSHI KURASHDAGI INSTITUTSIONAL AHAMIYATI.....	403
Pulatov Dilshod Xaqberdiyevich, Abdiyev Mansur Musurmonovich	
KICHIK TADBIRKORLIK SUBYEKTLARIDA SOLIQ HISOBINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	408
Toshtemirov To'liqin Toirjonovich	
АКТИВИЗАЦИЯ ИНВЕСТИЦИОННОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ И ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ИНВЕСТИЦИЙ В СЕЛЬСКОМ ХОЗЯЙСТВЕ В УСЛОВИЯХ ПРИАРАЛЯ (НА ПРИМЕРЕ РЕСПУБЛИКИ КАРАКАЛПАКСТАН).....	411
Жоллыбеков Хурмет Бахыт улы	

KORPORATIV MUNOSABATLAR ISHTIROKCHILARINING HUQUQLARINI HIMOYA ETISH VA TA'MINLASHNING HUQUQIY-IQTISODIY SHAKLLARI.....	416
Rustamova Dilbar Rustamovna	
IQTISODIY TRANSFORMATSIYA SHAROITIDA STRATEGIK MENEJMENTNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING XORIJIY TAJRIBALARI	423
Ismadiyarov Alisher Abduraxmon o'g'li	
METALLURGIK TEXNOGEN CHIQINDILARDAN KAMYOB METALLARNI AJRATIB OLISH TEXNOLOGIYASI	427
Qayumov Oybek Azamat o'g'li, Ro'ziyev Ulug'bek Mamarasulovich, Abdullayev Farruh Odiljon o'g'li	
TRANSCHEGARAVIY ELEKTRON SAVDONI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHDA XO'JALIK ALOQALARI LOGISTIKASI.....	434
Yakubov Maksadxan Sultaniyazovich, Jumaboev Behzod	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA INVESTISIYALARNI JALB QILISH	443
Raimjanova Madina Asrarovna	
O'ZBEKISTONDA ZARGARLIK XIZMATLARI BOZORINI RIVOJLANTIRISH YO'LLARI	448
Azizova Roxila Baxodir qizi	
XIZMAT KO'RSATISH KORXONALARI FAOLIYATIDA INVESTITSİYALARDAN FOYDALANISH SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASHNING EKONOMETRIK MODELLASHTIRISH	452
Isakova Naima Ikromjonovna	
RIVOJLANAYOTGAN MAMLAKATLAR IQTISODIYOTIDA AJ "HUDUDIY ELEKTR TARMOQLARI" MOLIYAVIY BARQARORLIGINI MUSTAHKAMLASH YO'LLARI	459
Bo'ranboyeva Shoir Rustamovna	
"QISHLOQ HUDUDLARIDA XOTIN-QIZLARNING BARQAROR TURMUSH TARZINI TA'MINLASHDA NODAVLAT NOTIJORAT TASHKILOTLARINING O'RNI VA AHAMIYATI"	466
Xoliyorova Shoxista Qahramon qizi, Niyozova Ruksora	
SMART TOURISM KAK INSTRUMENT USTOYCHIVOGO RAZVITIYA TURISTSKIX REGIONOV: MEJDUNARODNYY OPIYT I REGIONALNAYA ADAPTACIYA	471
Usmanova Aziza Bahodirovna	
XUFIYONA IQTISODIYOT KO'LAMINI QISQARTIRISHDA SOLIQ MA'MURCHILIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING TUTGAN O'RNI	477
Atamurodov To'liqin To'ymurodovich, Mamatkulov Salimjon Rahmonkulovich, Abdiyev Mansur Musurmonovich	
IQTISODIYOTDA TURIZM O'RNINI STATISTIK TAHLILINING XALQARO STANDARTLARI VA TAJRIBALARI	482
Jumanova Zilola Tuychiyevna	
INVESTITSIYA LOYIHALARINI MOLIYALASHTIRISH TIZIMIDA BANK KREDITLARINING O'RNI VA AHAMIYATI	489
Faxriddinov Temur Faxriddin o'g'li	
XALQARO MOLIYA BOZORLARIDAN MOLIYAVIY RESURSLARNI JALB ETISHDA SUVEREN KREDIT REYTINGLARINING O'RNI	494
Mamadaliyev Poziljon Mansurjon o'g'li	
XIZMAT KO'RSATISH SOHASIDA MIJOZLAR BILAN O'ZARO MUNOSABATLAR RIVOJLANISH HOLATI TAHLILI	500
Ismailova Ma'mura Eldorovna	
MILLIY SANOAT RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI OSHIRISHDA INSON KAPITALINING O'RNI	506
Yunusov Foziljon G'ulomqodirovich	
XONDIZA KONI POLIMETALL RUDALARINI FLOTATSIYALASHDA REAGENT REJIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	511
Shodiyev Abbas Ne'mat o'g'li, Egamberdiyev Baxtiyor Barat o'g'li	
EKSPORT-IMPORT OPERATSIYALARI BO'YICHA MUDDATI O'TGAN DEBITOR QARZDORLIKNI ANIQLASHDA RAQAMLI SOLIQ NAZORATI MONITORINGINING QO'LLANILISHI VA SAMARADORLIGI	517
Tashmuxe'dov Dilmurod Mirabzalovich	

SOLIQ SALOHİYATIGA TA’SIR ETUVCHI OMILLAR VA ULARNING TA’SIRI522
Jurayev Xusan Atamuratovich

IMPROVING MECHANISMS FOR ATTRACTING FOREIGN INVESTMENTS528
Sobirov A. Abdurasul

MUNDARIJA • СОДЕРЖАНИЕ • CONTENTS

IMPROVING MECHANISMS FOR ATTRACTING FOREIGN INVESTMENTS

Sobirov A. Abdurasul

PhD., Head of the Department of "Social and Economic Sciences"

Institute of Social and Political sciences

Tashkent, Uzbekistan

Abstract. The article describes contemporary mechanisms for attracting foreign investment and identifies key factors influencing investors' decisions in emerging and developing economies. The research analyzes institutional, legal, and economic conditions that shape investment attractiveness, with particular attention to regulatory transparency, political stability, and infrastructure development. Based on comparative analysis and international best practices, the paper proposes a set of practical recommendations aimed at improving national investment policies and enhancing competitiveness in the global investment market.

Keywords: foreign investment; investment climate; economic development; investment policy; institutional reform; competitiveness.

Annotatsiya. Maqolada xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb etishning zamonaviy mexanizmlari yoritilib, rivojlanayotgan va o'tish davridagi iqtisodiyotlarda investorlar qarorlariga ta'sir ko'rsatuvchi asosiy omillar aniqlanadi. Tadqiqot investitsiya jozibadorligini shakllantiruvchi institutsional, huquqiy va iqtisodiy shart-sharoitlarni tahlil qiladi hamda tartibga solishning shaffofligi, siyosiy barqarorlik va infratuzilma rivojiga alohida e'tibor qaratadi. Taqqoslama tahlil va xalqaro ilg'or tajribalar asosida milliy investitsiya siyosatini takomillashtirish hamda global investitsiya bozorida raqobatbardoshlikni oshirishga qaratilgan amaliy tavsiyalar ishlab chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: xorijiy investitsiyalar; investitsiya muhiti; iqtisodiy rivojlanish; investitsiya siyosati; institutsional islohotlar; raqobatbardoshlik.

Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются современные механизмы привлечения иностранных инвестиций и выявляются ключевые факторы, влияющие на инвестиционные решения в развивающихся и переходных экономиках. В исследовании анализируются институциональные, правовые и экономические условия, формирующие инвестиционную привлекательность, с особым акцентом на прозрачность регулирования, политическую стабильность и развитие инфраструктуры. На основе сравнительного анализа и международной передовой практики предложен комплекс практических рекомендаций, направленных на совершенствование национальной инвестиционной политики и повышение конкурентоспособности на глобальном инвестиционном рынке.

Ключевые слова: иностранные инвестиции; инвестиционный климат; экономическое развитие; инвестиционная политика; институциональные реформы; конкурентоспособность.

INTRODUCTION

The relevance of this study is determined by the growing role of foreign investments in ensuring economic growth, technological modernization, and integration into the global economy. In conditions of intensified international competition for capital, countries must continuously improve their investment mechanisms to remain attractive to foreign investors. Therefore, the development of effective, transparent, and stable investment frameworks has become a priority for national economic strategies.

International capital movement among countries has accelerated as a result of globalization and international economic integration. Foreign direct investment (FDI) represents one of the most significant drivers of national economic development. According to available sources, global FDI declined by 12 percent to USD 1.3 trillion in 2022. Particular attention was devoted to this issue in the Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 29, 2019, "On Measures to Further Improve Mechanisms for Attracting Foreign Direct Investment

into the National Economy,” which prioritized enhancing the efficiency of FDI attraction and informing foreign investors about the opportunities and potential of the country [1].

Based on the foregoing, the development of effective strategies for attracting and utilizing foreign direct investment in the national economy demonstrates that research efforts are aimed at ensuring the compatibility of state and market mechanisms in achieving regional competitive advantages. Investment potential, investment risk levels, and investment inflows are therefore of primary importance. Existing studies extensively address various methods of attracting foreign direct investment, with particular emphasis on venture, concession, and franchising approaches. However, issues related to improving state regulatory mechanisms for foreign direct investment remain insufficiently explored in academic research.

In Uzbekistan’s practice, a number of proposals and recommendations have been developed to enhance the effectiveness of state regulation of foreign investment. These include: the formulation of a foreign direct investment (FDI) strategy based on the evolutionary development of Uzbekistan’s economy and its innovative achievements; the simultaneous establishment of an effective institutional framework, improvement of the business environment, and development of a system of legal incentives and guarantees for foreign investors, accompanied by a gradual transition from a preferential to a national treatment regime for FDI; the restriction of imports of obsolete or low-quality technologies and the encouragement of research and development activities by foreign transnational corporations; the reduction of administrative barriers in FDI regulation through greater transparency in licensing procedures and the expansion of government consultations with foreign entrepreneurs prior to the adoption of new measures.

Furthermore, regional policies for attracting FDI should be improved by focusing on the utilization of regional resource potential in accordance with development priorities. This includes the formation of an infrastructure-institutional complex, the design of regional investment development programs, the systematization of regional competition and marketing strategies for FDI attraction, the elimination of procedural and institutional constraints, and the adaptation of free economic zone concepts to international best practices. In addition, the role of knowledge-intensive investments should be strengthened by promoting the transfer of advanced technologies into promising sectors through FDI, implementing a state program for high-technology industrial modernization, ensuring the effective use of tax incentives, and providing local support to foreign producers.

It is essential to study the experience of developed countries, including their legislative frameworks for improving the investment climate, policy decisions aimed at economic development, and methodological approaches to attracting investment, and to adapt these practices to Uzbekistan’s specific conditions. The application of accumulated international experience, while considering national characteristics, helps reduce risks, avoid excessive abstraction, and ensure higher efficiency.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The combination of foreign investment and national resources accelerates the adoption of advanced technologies, improves workforce qualifications, and promotes the efficient use of local production capacities, ultimately generating a significant synergistic effect. From foreign researchers such as R.Vernon focuses on the relationship between foreign direct investment (FDI) and international trade within the theory of international product production [4]. In this framework, he integrates elements of international economic relations—such as international trade, production, and the causes of industrial relocation—with marketing theory, particularly the product life-cycle curve. Within the theory of multinational corporations and imperfect competition, the Canadian economist Stephen Hymer analyzed the competitiveness of multinational enterprises (MNEs) and their international activities [5]. In the theory of foreign direct investment and the competitive advantage of nations, M.Porter examined the competitiveness of FDI recipient countries and explored the relationship between foreign direct investment and national competitiveness [6]. Several economists from our republic, including B.A. Vakhobov defines foreign direct investment as “investments that enable the investor to exercise effective control over economic activity, including ownership of at least 10% of a company’s shares or equity capital” [7]. In his scholarly studies, N.N. Oblomurodov examines macroeconomic factors influencing the improvement of the FDI attraction system and emphasizes that investment attractiveness and investment activity play a crucial role in enhancing this system [8]. According to Bekmurodov, foreign direct investment allows investors to export capital directly, granting them the right to control the enterprise, which consequently becomes a foreign subsidiary of the parent company [9]. A.B.Sotvoldiev argues that direct investments are a key factor in the sustainable development of regions, as they create conditions for rapid industrial growth, ensure sufficient capital inflows, and form the foundation for expanded reproduction [10].

According to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Investments and Investment Activity,” foreign direct investment is defined as investment carried out by a foreign investor without state guarantees, using either own or borrowed funds [3].

In the context of globalization and market relations, national economies face intense competition for global investment, and this struggle continues in a systematic and sustained manner. The deregulation of foreign economic activity, improvement of legal, social, and socio-economic conditions for attracting foreign direct investment, the implementation of an open-door policy toward foreign capital, and the prioritization of sectors that ensure economic independence and the production of competitive goods constitute the fundamental principles of investment policy [12]. Alongside the achievements attained in the Republic, a number of challenges related to investment attraction remain, and their resolution is crucial for the future development of Uzbekistan [13].

Thus, Uzbekistan has demonstrated in practice that it is a reliable and solvent partner and that favorable conditions for foreign investment have been established in the country. Consequently, modernization, technical and technological upgrading, and the effective orientation of foreign investment toward the national economy represent some of the most critical issues of the contemporary era. Uzbekistan possesses substantial potential and broad opportunities to address these priorities successfully.

For Uzbekistan, where the education system is undergoing substantial transformation, the attraction of foreign investment represents a crucial instrument for accelerating modernization processes. Within the framework of reforms aimed at improving educational quality, developing infrastructure, and expanding access to educational services, foreign investment plays a significant role in strengthening the education sector and facilitating its integration into the international academic community.

These efforts are reflected in a number of key state-level initiatives. Uzbekistan is actively engaged in enhancing educational standards, modernizing educational institutions, and creating favorable conditions for attracting external investment into educational development programs. Priority areas include the promotion of international cooperation, the implementation of joint projects with foreign universities and research institutions, and the integration of innovative technologies into the learning process. Collectively, these initiatives form part of a broader national strategy focused on human capital development and increasing the country's global competitiveness.

Foreign investment is a decisive factor in the modernization of educational infrastructure, the establishment of new academic programs, and the adoption of advanced technologies. A successful example is provided by the United Kingdom, where public–private partnership mechanisms were widely applied through the Private Finance Initiative (PFI), introduced in the early 1990s [14]. This program enabled the mobilization of private capital for the construction of educational institutions, the provision of educational services, and infrastructure modernization. Between 1992 and 2020, more than £65 billion was invested in educational projects through PFI, resulting in significant improvements in service quality [15].

This experience is particularly relevant for Uzbekistan, where funding constraints in educational infrastructure remain acute, especially in rural areas. The implementation of similar public–private partnership models could facilitate the modernization of schools and universities.

Another notable example is the United States, where foreign investment is actively directed toward educational technologies and startups. Online platforms such as Coursera and Khan Academy were established with the support of international investors and universities, enabling the creation of accessible educational resources and the introduction of innovative learning approaches [16]. In 2022 alone, total investment in educational startups exceeded USD 5 billion [17]. In Uzbekistan, this model could serve as a foundation for the development of online education, particularly given the growing relevance of distance learning technologies during the pandemic. The expansion of online education and the establishment of educational platforms supported by international investment would contribute to Uzbekistan's integration into the global educational community and ensure access to high-quality education for students in remote regions.

China also demonstrates extensive utilization of foreign investment in the development of international education. The country has established numerous joint educational programs with foreign universities, leading to improved educational quality and deeper international cooperation [18].

Germany's experience further highlights the importance of foreign investment in education, not only in infrastructure development but also in teacher training and research advancement. Government programs in Germany focus on improving professional training in educational institutions, which positively influences educational quality [19]. Attracting foreign investment for teacher training and joint academic programs with international universities could help address one of Uzbekistan's key challenges—enhancing faculty qualifications, particularly in information technology and innovative teaching methodologies.

Ultimately, integration into the international educational community is essential for establishing modern educational standards aligned with global trends. To achieve this objective, Uzbekistan must continue implementing reforms aimed at improving accessibility and quality through foreign investment, thereby strengthening its position within the global education system.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study employs a mixed-methods research design based on secondary data collection from international databases, official investment statistics, policy documents, and institutional reports. Quantitative data are analyzed using comparative and trend analysis, while qualitative information is examined through content analysis to identify key institutional, regulatory, and economic factors affecting foreign investment attraction and policy effectiveness.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

As a result of a comparative analysis of theoretical perspectives and practical approaches reflecting the economic nature of foreign direct investment (FDI), several key characteristics can be identified. First, FDI is associated with entrepreneurial activity in the host country. Second, it is primarily directed toward the development of the real sector of the economy, thereby determining the production structure. Third, FDI implies the investor's ability to participate in enterprise management and to influence operational decisions. Additional defining features include the large scale of investments, a high level of risk, an orientation toward access to foreign markets, the exploitation of overseas resources, and the long-term nature of investment commitments.

The potential positive effects of attracting FDI to a host country include the following. FDI contributes to economic growth and increases overall investment efficiency; it encourages the reinvestment of profits generated within the host economy; it facilitates the establishment of new enterprises, leading to job creation for the local population; it enhances the knowledge base of the workforce by providing opportunities for professional training and the development of managerial competencies; it enables access to advanced technologies, modern production methods, and best organizational practices; it stimulates competition in domestic markets and contributes to lower prices for goods and services; it positively affects the sectoral and regional structure of the host economy; and it increases government revenues through taxes, environmental fees, and other mandatory payments made by foreign enterprises.

In most cases, the qualitative and quantitative impact of FDI on a country's economy depends on the existence of a favorable investment climate in the host country and the effectiveness of state regulatory measures. Despite the diversity and national specificities of FDI regulation policies, their primary objective remains the attraction of an adequate volume of investment and its efficient and productive utilization. In recent years, a major trend has been the formalization and liberalization of FDI regulation in both developed and developing countries. This liberalization involves opening previously restricted regions and sectors to foreign capital, simplifying administrative procedures, expanding incentives, reducing tax burdens, and increasing transparency for foreign investors.

Investment attractiveness assessment and the identification of economic potential create a solid analytical foundation for informed investor decision-making. In Uzbekistan, the ongoing enhancement of the investment climate reflects a strategic national priority aimed at expanding foreign capital inflows. Achieving this objective requires the consistent implementation of a coherent national investment policy that clearly defines strategic priorities, introduces effective incentive mechanisms, and ensures regulatory clarity through a well-structured legal framework. International practice confirms that countries implementing proactive investment policies tend to achieve sustainable economic growth, as investment serves as a key engine of structural transformation and development. The expansion of capital inflows and the commissioning of new production capacities are expected to accelerate economic growth, which in turn generates favorable conditions for addressing long-standing socio-economic challenges in a systematic manner.

At the same time, further improvement in the quality of investment proposals and feasibility studies represents an important area for institutional development. Strengthening methodological support for entrepreneurs through coordinated assistance from local authorities, commercial banks, and regional chambers of commerce would contribute to greater compliance with international and national standards. Enhancing the financial and economic preparedness of project initiators through preliminary assessments and advisory mechanisms can improve project sustainability and increase their inclusion in investment and regional development programs.

The effectiveness of foreign investment attraction may also be strengthened by expanding the role of local authorities in disseminating comprehensive and up-to-date information on regional investment opportunities. The establishment of regional digital platforms presenting investment potential, project pipelines, and business proposals, alongside the organization of targeted conferences, seminars, and international investment forums, is expected to improve investor awareness and confidence. As these measures are implemented, the efficiency of foreign investment utilization is projected to increase, supporting the rational allocation of capital and maximizing its developmental impact. In this context, foreign investment is anticipated to play a catalytic role in socio-economic development, particularly by enabling the integration of previously underutilized natural, industrial, and labor resources into productive economic activity.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Thus, improving mechanisms for attracting foreign investments requires a comprehensive approach that combines regulatory reform, institutional strengthening, and the creation of a favorable business environment. The implementation of consistent and transparent investment policies enhances investor confidence and contributes to long-term economic stability. The proposed recommendations can serve as a practical basis for policymakers seeking to increase foreign investment inflows and promote sustainable economic development. A defining characteristic of Uzbekistan's investment climate is its status as the most stable country in Central Asia, which is directly linked to the investment policy pursued by the state. In the contemporary global economy, the future development of any nation largely depends on the volume and quality of investment inflows. Investment plays a particularly significant role in the social, economic, and political advancement of countries. The distinctiveness of Uzbekistan's investment policy lies in its prioritization of projects aimed at establishing new high-technology industries that enable deep processing of domestic raw materials. It is evident that the investment policy designed to attract a broader range of capital into the national economy has become a crucial foundation for the effective implementation of economic reforms.

List of used literature:

1. Resolution No. PD-4300 of April 29, 2019 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures for the further improvement of mechanisms for attracting direct foreign investment into the national economy". <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/7571137>
2. Kruminya, V. A. Improving the Organizational and Economic Mechanism for Attracting Foreign Direct Investment in the Era of Digitalization. 2021.
3. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "About investments and investment activities" dated December 25, 2019, No. LRU-598. Available at: <https://lex.uz/docs/4664142>
4. Vernon R. International investment and international trade in the product cycle // Quarterly Journal of Economics. 016. No 80. P. 190-207.
5. Stephen Hymer. The Multinational Firm and Multinational Corporate Capital. –<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/267547912>
6. Porter M. International competition. -M.: Alpina Publisher, 2019. -947 p.
7. Vakhobov A.B. Foreign Investments: A Textbook. – Tashkent: Moliya, 2010.
8. Oblomurodov N.N. Theoretical Foundations and Priorities for Attracting Foreign Direct Investments: A Monograph. – Tashkent: Science and Technology, 2009. – 108 p.
9. Bekmurodov A. et al. Foreign Investments: A Textbook. – Tashkent: TDIU, 2011. – 196 p.
10. Sotvoldiev B. Ways to Increase the Scale of Direct Investment in the Context of Economic Modernization (using the Andijan Region as an Example). IQT. Science. Abstract. – Tashkent: 2019. – 10 p.
11. Насиров Д. Ф., Алиева Х. ПРИВЛЕЧЕНИЕ ИНВЕСТИЦИОННЫХ ПОТОКОВ В ЭКОНОМИКУ УЗБЕКИСТАНА // Journal of marketing, business and management. – 2025. – Т. 3. – №. 10. – С. 42-45.
12. Vakhobov, A.V., Khadzhibakiev, Sh.Kh., & Muminov, N.G. Foreign Investments. Methodological manual. Tashkent: "Finance", 2010, 153 p.
13. Teshabaeva, O.N., Muhammadov, I.B.O., & Jamoliddinov, D.R. (2020). The role of investments in the development of the agricultural sector of the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In Financial, legal, and innovative aspects of investment in regional economies (pp. 600–603).
14. Hodge, G. A., & Greve, C. (2007). Public-Private Partnerships: An International Performance Review. Public Administration Review, 67(3), 545-558.
15. Bauer, M. W., & Gaskell, G. (2002). Quality, Quantification, and the Research Process: A Study of International Educational Projects. Social Science Research Methods in Education (pp. 125-140).
16. Li, J., & Zhang, X. (2013). International Education and Cooperation in China: Trends and Future Prospects. Journal of Higher Education Policy, 26(3), 361-374.
17. Wagner, A., & Becker, S. (2020). Foreign Investment in Education: The Role of International Funds in Academic Institutions. Journal of Global Education, 44(4), 367-384.
18. Schneider, J., & Stadelmann, C. (2017). Investment in Education and Teacher Development: A Comparative Study of Germany's Educational Reforms. European Journal of Education and Training, 59(2), 124-140.
19. World Bank (2019). Investing in Education for Sustainable Development: Global Strategies and Approaches. World Bank Education Reports, 5, 43-56.
20. Sobirovna K. D., Gafurovich A. N., Abdugafarovich S. A. Forming a management system of organizational culture of the enterprise. – 2021.
21. Sobirov A. A. TO 'G 'RIDAN-TO 'G 'RI XORIJIY INVESTITSIYALARNING O 'ZBEKISTONDA IQTISODIY BARQARORLIKNI TA'MINLASHDAGI AHAMIYATI VA UNING DINAMIK TAHLILI //Innovation Science and Technology. – 2025. – Т. 1. – №. 11.

muhandislik

& iqtisodiyot

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir Alibekov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Abdurahmon Qurbonov

2026. № 1

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Muhandislik va iqtisodiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelamasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

"Muhandislik va iqtisodiyot" jurnali 26.06.2023-yildan
O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi
Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan
№S-5669245 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: №095310.

**Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahri Yunusobod
tumani 15-mavze 19-uy**

+998 93 718 40 07

<https://muhandislik-iqtisodiyot.uz/index.php/journal>

t.me/yait_2100